

4. R. S. SAXENA and S. S. SHEHLWANT, *J. Prakt. Chemie.*, 1974, **316**, 517.
5. R. S. SAXENA and U. S. CHATURVEDI, *Monatshfte.*, 1973, **104**, 1208.
6. D. D. DEFORD and D. N. HUME, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 532.
7. D. N. HUME, D. D. DEFORD and G. C. B. CAVE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5323.

Mercury(II) Complexes with Substituted Aminobenzothiazoles

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CAMPBELL and his coworkers have reported¹ cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes with 2-amino-benzothiazole. Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) with substituted amino thiazoles have also been studied^{2,3} in detail. The present communication describes the reactions of 2-amino-6-methyl benzothiazole and 2-amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole towards mercury(II) ion.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The substituted aminobenzothiazoles have been prepared by standard procedure.

A mixture of methanol solutions of the mercury salt and the substituted aminobenzothiazole (1 : 2 ratio) was refluxed (15 minutes to 1 hour) and cooled when crystalline compounds separated out. These were filtered, washed with methanol followed by ether and dried in vacuo.

Mercury content in the complexes was estimated complexometrically by EDTA method and nitrogen

and sulfur by standard procedure. Conductance was measured in 10⁻³M acetone solution using Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge. IR spectra were recorded in KBr phase using Unicam SP-1025 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

All the ten complexes reported in the present investigation are of the type [HgL₂X₂], where L=2-amino-6-methylbenzothiazole and 2-amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole, and X=Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, NO₃⁻, SCN⁻, OAc⁻. The complexes are white to greyish white in colour, have low melting points and are soluble in acetone, the solution being non-electrolytes (Λ_M being in the range of 20-30 mhos. cm²).

The appearance of a sharp peak in the IR spectra around 815 cm⁻¹ in the free ligands can be assigned to $\nu(C-S)$ vibration. On complexation with Hg(II) ion, this frequency has been shifted down to lower frequency region ~800 cm⁻¹ indicating possible bonding of benzothiazole to the metal ion through the ring sulfur atom. The bands observed ~1535 cm⁻¹ and 3250 cm⁻¹ in free ligand are due to $\nu(C=N)$ and $\nu(N-H)$ vibrations respectively. No remarkable shift of these two bands has been noticed in the complexes, which proves that both the endo and exocyclic nitrogen atoms are not coordinated to the metal ion. The positions of $\nu(C-N)$, $\nu(C-S)$ and δNCS bands in the thiocyanato complex are indicative of S-bonded thiocyanate⁴⁻⁷. The carboxylates give⁸ a strong asymmetric stretching band near 1650-1550 cm⁻¹ and a weaker symmetrical stretching band near 1400 cm⁻¹. In the present investigation two sharp peaks appeared at 1650 cm⁻¹ and 1395 cm⁻¹, which can be assignable to $\nu(C=O)_{as}$ and $\nu(C=O)_s$ vibrations.

In the nitrate complex ν_4 and ν_1 bands (NO₃ asymmetric and symmetric stretch) appear at 1450 cm⁻¹ and 1280 cm⁻¹ respectively. The position of ν_4 and ν_1 and their separation $\Delta\nu$ of 130 cm⁻¹ suggests^{9,10}, the nitrate group to be monodentate.

TABLE I—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, IR AND FUNGICIDAL DATA OF Hg(II) COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Compound	Λ_M mhos cm ²	%Hg		%Nitrogen		%Sulfur		(C-S)	%Inhibition	
			Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.		<i>P. oryzae</i> 400 ppm	<i>H. oryzae</i> 1000 ppm
1.	HgL ₂ Cl ₂	26.5	30.97	31.32	8.59	8.74	9.74	9.99	800	—	—
2.	HgL ₂ Br ₂	20.4	27.21	27.50	7.46	7.67	8.41	8.77	808	—	—
3.	HgL ₂ I ₂	10.8	24.08	24.36	6.67	6.80	7.58	7.77	805	—	—
4.	HgL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	20.2	28.53	28.93	11.95	12.11	9.08	9.22	798	—	—
5.	HgL ₂ (OAc) ₂	10.4	28.86	29.17	9.37	9.53	10.72	10.89	800	—	—
6.	HgL ₂ Cl ₂	12.8	33.08	33.46	9.18	9.36	10.46	10.67	800	—	—
7.	HgL' ₂ Br ₂	17.6	28.71	29.14	8.02	8.13	9.08	9.29	805	74.8/51.5	69.1/62.8
8.	HgL' ₂ I ₂	12.9	25.29	25.63	7.05	7.15	8.03	8.17	800	—	—
9.	HgL' ₂ (SCN) ₂	13.1	30.87	31.12	12.92	13.03	19.68	19.85	795	64.9/21.8	59.3/18.6
10.	HgL' ₂ (OAc) ₂	10.7	30.75	31.02	8.53	8.66	9.72	9.89	805	60.0/18.3	66.1/32.2

L=2-Amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole, L'=2-Amino-6-methyl benzothiazole.

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On the basis of analytical and conductance data the complexes presumably have tetrahedral configuration around the metal ion.

The fungitoxicity of three complexes have been studied against rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* (Cav.) and brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae* at various concentrations. All the three complexes have shown significant activity against *P. oryzae*, particularly at 400 ppm and 1000 ppm. Compound no. 7 is also found to be active against *H. oryzae* at both the concentrations. So this compound can also be used as a suitable fungicide because of its prominent fungitoxicity.

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References

1. M. J. M. CAMPBELL, D. W. CORD, R. GRZESKOWISK and M. GOLDSTEIN, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 672.
2. P. P. SINGH and A. K. SRIVASTAR, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1974, 27, 500.
3. B. S. MANHAS, V. K. BHATIA and O. P. CHITKARA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14(A), 3, 206.
4. J. CHATT and L. A. DUNCANSON, *Nature*, 1956, 178, 997.
5. A. TURCO and C. PECILE, *Nature*, 1961, 191, 66.
6. J. L. BURKHISTER, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, 1, 205, and 1968, 3, 225.
7. A. H. NORBURY and A. I. P. SINHA, *Quart. Rev.*, 1970, 24, 59.
8. K. NAKAMOTO, 'Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds', John Wiley, New York, 1970.
9. A. B. P. LEVER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 1042.
10. N. LOGN and W. SIMPSON, *Spectro Chim. Acta.*, 1965, 21, 857.

Reactions of Metal β -Diketonates-III. Reactions of Bis(Acetylacetonato) Cobalt(II) with Chelating Ligands

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In continuation of our work on the reactions of metal- β -diketonates^{1,2}, we have done some reactions of bis(acetylacetonato) cobalt(II), $\text{Co}(\text{ACAC})_2$ with different chelating ligands; e.g. ethylenediamine (=EN), orthoaminophenol (=OAP-H), glycine (=GLY-H), anthranilic acid (=AA-H), semicarbazide(=SC-H) and thiosemicarbazide(=TSC-H). This note also includes the reactions of

$\text{Co}(\text{ACAC})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with the Schiff bases N-phenylsalicylaldimine (=SAN-H), N-(2-hydroxyl)-Phenyl salicylaldimine (=SOAP-H₂) and N,N¹-ethylene bis(Salicylaldimine) (=BSEN-H₂).

Treatment of $\text{Co}(\text{ACAC})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{Co}(\text{ACAC})_2$ with EN, OAP-H, GLY-H and SAN-H in boiling toluene yielded mixed-ligand chelates of cobalt (II and III) of the types $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{ACAC})_2(\text{EN})]$, (I); $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}(\text{ACAC})(\text{OAP})_2]$ (III); $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}(\text{ACAC})(\text{GLY})_2]$ (IV); and $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{ACAC})(\text{SAN}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (VIII) respectively. Aerial oxidation of ethanolic solution of (I) and subsequent treatment with saturated aqueous solution of sodium perchlorate yielded a cobalt(III) complex, $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}(\text{ACAC})_2(\text{EN})]\text{ClO}_4$, (II). On the other hand, complete exchange of ACAC anion was observed when the title complex was reacted with AA-H and SOAP-H₂ in refluxing ethanol/toluene to yield $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{AA})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{SOAP}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (VII) respectively. However, the reaction (refluxing 20 min under N₂) of $\text{Co}(\text{ACAC})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with BSEN-H₂ in ethanol yielded the well-known complex, $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{BSEN})$. As observed previously³ the above reaction, when carried out in excess of air, yielded green crystalline complex, $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}(\text{BSEN})(\text{ACAC})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. It is interesting to note that the reactions of SC-H and TSC-H with $\text{Co}(\text{ACAC})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ yielded complexes of cobalt(II) of the types $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{ASC}-\text{H})_2$ (VI) and $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{ATSC}-\text{H})_2$ (V) respectively (where, ASC-H₂=semicarbazone of acetylacetone and ATSC-H₂=thiosemicarbazone of acetylacetone). Similar observations have been made when $\text{Ni}(\text{ACAC})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{Cu}(\text{ACAC})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ reacts with above two carbazides and the mechanism for the condensation of C=O group with the -NH₂ group to form -C=N group may be explained as discussed previously^{1,2,4}.

The elemental analyses (Table 1) support the formulations of the present cobalt(II and III) chelates. The diamagnetic nature of the compounds (II), (III) and (IV) (Table 1) support the presence of trivalent cobalt in these chelates; while the paramagnetic nature of the rest of the complexes (Table 1) suggest the presence of bivalent cobalt in these chelates.

The observed magnetic moment value of 4.45 B.M. (Table 1) for $\text{Co}(\text{ATSC}-\text{H})_2$ (V) suggests a tetrahedral geometry^{5,6} for the complex. On the other hand, the μ_{eff} values for $\text{Co}(\text{ASC}-\text{H})_2$ (VI) and $\text{Co}(\text{ACAC})(\text{SAN}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (VIII) are found to be 4.90 B.M. and 4.99 B.M. respectively, which are suggestive of an octahedral structure for each of these complexes. The complexes $\text{Co}(\text{BSEN})$, (IX) ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=2.24$ B.M.) and $\text{Co}(\text{SOAP})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$, (VII) ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=2.45$ B.M.) are square planar.

The electronic spectral data of some of these complexes and their tentative assignments are given in Table 2. Based on magnetic and spectral data,